

Social Media Used in Language Learning of Students

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ABSTRACT: The main purpose of this study is to understand the experiences of students on how they used social media in language learning. Specifically, this study aimed to identify the benefits of social media as well as the challenges encountered by the students in using these tools. This qualitative phenomenological study was conducted among the 10 BSEd Third Year students of the Davao del Sur State College. Moreover, research showed how social media could make learning more interactive through authentic learning, native speaker engagement, auditory & visual resources and real time practice. Result also pointed out some issues, like distractions, misleading content and overloaded content. Based from the result, it is recommended for the teachers to guide students on how to choose reliable sources while encouraging critical thinking to avoid inaccurate information.

KEYWORDS: social media used, language learning, phenomenology

I. INTRODUCTION

Social media offers opportunities for engagement and interaction. However, learners may easily be sidetracked by unrelated content, leading to losing on their language learning. Additionally, the informal nature of social media might blur the lines between language learning and personal use, making it challenging for all educators to guide and monitor their students. Therefore, applying the benefits of social media for language learning while mitigating distraction is a significant challenge for educators seeking to assimilate these platforms into their curriculum. Hence it is emphasized that in order to be good at speaking, writing, reading, and listening, one should know how to utilize social media for language learning (Prihatini et al., 2023)

Moreover, data shows the negative side of using social media. In a study conducted in Indonesia, initial finding showed that social media particularly Facebook, Youtube, Instagram, and WhatsApp were not used properly, wasting some of its benefits and potentials for language learning (Nasution, A.K.P. 2022). Likewise, these applications were found to have limitations such as conflicting information concerns and many distractions (Zhou, 2022). Another problem of social media usage is the connectivity constraint and the potentially distracting content suggestions which provide irrelevant information (Kadek et al., 2021)

In the Philippines, a study regarding the quality of information accessed on social media, including exposure to fake news, faulty grammar, and senseless content, which can hinder language learning (Nanquil, 2020). As stated in PRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research in Davao City towards Senior High School Students there is a limited understanding of the language due to lack of daily usage opportunities (Cabillon, 2023). Challenges in using social media, like Facebook, for language learning in the Philippines State University include risks of cheating, limited comfort in arguing, and the need for teacher guidance for interactive learning (Nacionales, 2023).

Another issue is seen in online learning, as social media may pose language barriers, fragmented content, and the lack of real-time interaction which hinders language learning (Lin et al., 2024). Likewise, Facebook is a burden as this can provide technical issues like limited internet connectivity which can hinder its effectiveness in learning the target language (Nanquil, 2020). Additionally, distractions and conflicting information on social media could hinder the language learning process (Khan, F. U, et al., 2023).

This study is anchored from the perspective of Piaget's Cognitive Development Theory which focused on enhancing students' engagement and critical thinking in learning a language (Idham & Halod, 2024). These engagements align to both cognitive and social constructivism principles extending learning to students in an accessible shared task (Schrader, 2015). Moreover, this theory is applicable in this study as social media platforms such as Facebook, Youtube, WhatsApp, Google Meet demonstrate

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improved social media engagement aligned o Vygotsky’s Constructivist Theory in enhancing students’ performance in English language learning (Umar et al., 2023).

This qualitative-phenomenological study addressed the gap in understanding student’s nuanced experiences with social media for language learning. While previous research has examined the general effectiveness of social media in education, particularly its impact on learning language (Ariantini et al., 2021) There is a scarcity of comprehensive qualitative studies focusing on students’ lived experiences, perceptions, and challenges with social media specifically for language learning. By delving into these experiences, this study aims to provide educators and researchers with valuable insights to better support students’ needs in utilizing social media as tools for learning language in a meaningful and relevant ways.

II. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This study aimed to understand the experiences of students with the used of social media in language learning. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions.

1. What are the experiences of the students using social media to engage in language learning?
2. What are the benefits of using social media to engage in language learning?

III. METHOD

Respondents and Instruments

This study intended for the college students particularly the 3rd Year BSED-English students who were officially enrolled at Davao Del Sur State College, Mati, Digos City. These students were chosen to be interviewed and answer the prepared questionnaires so that the researcher obtained the necessary data for this study. The researcher picked only 10 participants from 3rd Year BSED-English. The participants are involved in one-on-one interviews. The data were collected through individual interviews with interview guide created by the researcher and had undergone the process of validation. The interview guide comprised of three (3) main questions and ten (10) probing questions were used to achieve the objectives of the study and to answer the research questions.

Design and Procedure

This qualitative research design utilized a phenomenological approach. The suggested phenomenological qualitative design offered procedures that sharpened the level on ongoing issue in phenomenologically approach of the qualitative research (Giorgi, 2006). Thus, this approach examined individual’s everyday experienced and gained more understanding of how individuals described those experiences.

The collected data was analyzed using (Braun et. Al., 2016) Thematic Analysis of Transcribed Data. After gathering “thick descriptions,” the next step in the research process was data analysis using the specific procedure. For this to be achieved, the researcher transcribed the answers first from the intended beneficiaries or participants. Since the interview transcripts were in Cebuano (native language of the students), the proponents translated the responses to English based on the context to ensure functional and cultural equivalence. Then, the transcriptions were analyzed using thematic analysis.

According to (Maguire and Delahunt, 2017), thematic analysis is a process for analyzing and identifying patterns (themes) within the qualitative data. They stated further that a theme captured something significant regarding the data in connection to the research question and shows a level of patterned answers or meaning in the data sources. They also discussed that a theme became significant when it captured something meaningful in accordance to the overall research objectives.

Ethical Consideration

When doing research, it is essential to follow ethical rules. Hence, researchers needed to get permission from people involved in the study, so they would understand what is going on and why it is happening. Research participants were free to stop being part of the study whenever they want. Researchers gave enough information so they could decide if they want to participate.

Additionally, it is important for the researchers to make sure they considered the ethical rules such as getting permission, potential risks, keeping things private, and not sharing people’s name. This means that anyone helping with collecting data for the research study needed to fully understand what the study is all about, know what is being shared, and be able to choose if they want to participate. Lastly, in the research methodology part, it is significant to present reliability and validity in a precise and accurate manner. To evaluate the integrity and strength of a research process it is important to used validity and reliability in research study (Woodrow, 2014).

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This section summarized the findings of the qualitative research in response to the interview guide questionnaire gathered from

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the answers of the ten (10) 3rd Year BSED-English college participants. The results and findings were transcribed and thematically analyzed from the interview results and then classified in specific category known as emerging themes. For each research question, tables were used to present the results of the data analysis and interpretations of the findings.

Experiences of the Students Using Social Media to Engage in Language Learning

Research Question 1 aimed to understand the experiences of the students using social media to engage in language learning at Davao Del Sur State College. From the transcripts, codes were identified, categorized to four emerging themes, namely: *real-life context*, *accessibility & convenience*, *misleading content*, and *overload information*.

Table 1: Experiences of the Students Using social media to Engage in Language Learning

Core Ideas	Themes
In order to acquire vocabulary and pronunciation, students follow native speakers on websites like YouTube, Instagram and Tiktok. Participating in real-world discussion and language learning community like Facebook enhances speaking and listening abilities. Authentic language content, including podcast, videos, and social media post, offers an opportunity to learn through social media.	Real-Life Context
Social media provides flexible learning anytime and anywhere, compared to traditional approaches. Due to the availability of a variety of language learning apps and resources, students may easily practice grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation. Compared to traditional learning resources, students believe social media platforms to be more approachable and engaging.	Accessibility and Convenience
Learners may become confused by insufficient grammar recommendations, simplistic instruction, and inaccurate translations on social media. Slang, acronyms, and casual language used online might not always be accurate in the given context. Entertainment value may take precedence over instructional correctness in social media information, which could result in misunderstandings.	Misleading Content
The abundance of content on social media might overwhelm students, making it challenging for them to concentrate on pertinent information. Diverse content is frequently bombarded learners via social media platforms, thus taking away from targeted language learning. Filtering through irrelevant or untrustworthy posts adds even another level of complexity to social media learning.	Overload Information

Data showed that students found specific benefits of social media. Real – life context activities in vocabulary and pronunciation can be learned through YouTube, TikTok, Facebook, etc. Learning with social media is accessible and convenient for the learners since they can access it anytime they want without reading a lot in books using conventional method. However, learning can be misleading as there are contents which are insufficient due to very simplistic explanation. Another issue is filtering of irrelevant information which adds even more complexity of language learning.

In support to this, Fajriah et al. (2024) emphasized that YouTube was the most utilized platform for English learning, aiding students in improving listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills through video content and interaction with native speakers. In a substantial study of (Akpan, et.al., 2022) through accessibility of social media, it enhances flexibility in language learning, allowing the students to practice anytime, which increased their motivation and engagement compared with traditional methods. Despite benefits, Nanquil (2020) study showed that learners may experience misleading information due to fake news and incorrect grammar in social media, which negatively affected their language learning.

Benefits of Using Social Media to Engage in Language Learning

This second objective aimed to understand the benefits of using social media platforms to engage in language learning at Davao Del Sur State College. Three emerging themes were identified, namely: *learning through social media*, *interactive learning tool*, and *learning opportunities*.

Table 2: Benefits of Using social media to Engage in Language Learning

Core Ideas	Themes
Being exposed to natural speakers and discussions in real life. Availability of many media formats (posts, podcasts, videos). Picking up colloquialisms and idioms from social media.	<i>Authentic Language Learning</i>

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The ability to learn at anytime, anyplace. Tailored educational opportunities according to individual preferences. Looking into several language-learning platforms.	<i>Self-Paced Learning</i>
Watch videos to improve your listening and pronouncing skills. Educational materials such as tutorials and podcasts. Quick, interesting videos for focused learning.	<i>Auditory & Visual Resources</i>
Applying language skills through comments and messaging on social media. Having discussions in real time with other students or native speakers. Using grammatical and vocabulary exercises in real-life situations.	<i>Real-Time Practice</i>

Social media provide interaction which allowed the learners to observe how language is applied in real-life situations which could helped them understand better how native speakers expressed themselves in different situations. These real-time interactions simulate real-life situations, allowing them to practice speaking, listening, and writing in a more authentic way. The ability of the participants to learn anytime and anywhere could take control with their own schedules. Also, the flexibility of their time is an advantage of using social media platforms for their learning, where they could dig deeper with the different materials and practice at their own pace.

In relation to the study of (Chik, 2020), social media immerses learners in real life language experiences which allows learners to be engaged with various contents and multilingual resources enhancing their understanding of language (Chik, 2020). Moreover, Alkamel (2024) social media platforms facilitate authentic communication, allow learners to receive quick feedback from native speakers. In support to this study, (Shykun, 2024) explained that online platforms can provide a flexible and autonomy in learning which is convenient for the learners to study in their own pace.

Supporting this claim, Islam (2022) discovered that watching videos on social media improves listening and pronunciation by offering authentic language exposure and interactive learning opportunities through real time engagement with native speakers and content creators. Another author noted that platforms like Facebook and Youtube enhanced learners listening and pronunciation by exposing them to authentic language use, making them effective interactive tools in language learning Anisimova (2020).

V. CONCLUSION

The result of this study showed that social media platforms provide an interactive environment towards students' language learning. Many participants improved their vocabulary and pronunciation by following native speakers on platforms such as Youtube, Tiktok, and any other platforms. Participants are engaged in online communities' group and participated in real-world to develop their language learning.

One of the benefits using social media platforms for language learning is the accessibility and easy to use. Participants could work on their grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation whenever they want using different language apps and resources. The nature of social media, with its videos, kept learners engaged and motivated. However, some of the participants experiencing misleading of the

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research findings on social media used in language learning among college students, recommendations are put into account. These are:

School Administrators. They may consider integrating social media platforms in students' language learning programs, offering it as a flexible tool for interactive learning. However, they need to ensure learners are well guided on how to used reliable sources and balance social media together with the traditional methods to avoid learners' confusion from misleading content.

Teachers. They can guide students on how choose reliable sources and content while encouraging critical thinking to avoid inaccurate information. In addition, teachers may create a balance between interactive, flexible nature of social media platforms, and language instruction, ensuring that learners received understanding of grammars and language rules.

Students. Be mindful of the content that they engaged with, ensuring that it came from reliable sources to avoid confusion caused by inaccurate information. Additionally, learners could benefit from joining language communities and participating in real world discussions to enhanced learning.

Future Researchers. They might explore strategies to addressed the challenges of misleading content in social media platforms. Understanding how to better integrate social media in language learning to create a balanced and effective language learning environment that maximized both engagement and educational importance.

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